

**ISSUES OF INCREASING THE CAPACITY OF
ENTERPRISES TO EXPORT PRODUCTS****Sobirov Otabek Olimjonovich****Doctor of Economics (DSc), Associate Professor,****Namangan State Technical University.****Associate Professor of the Department of Accounting****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20176561>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 10th May 2026Accepted: 11th May 2026Online: 14th May 2026**KEYWORDS**

Export, costs, quality, import, raw materials, labor resources, international standards, income, innovative technologies, investment.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses important issues of increasing exports of products abroad by enterprises in the context of economic modernization, expanding the geography of exports when exporting products abroad, creating safe conditions for the production of products and ensuring systematic control in this regard, constantly expanding the production of competitive products, continuously producing a diverse range of products, and ensuring that manufactured products are produced in accordance with international standards.

The importance attached to the quality of products manufactured and sold by enterprises is increasing sharply. Therefore, modern technologies can produce efficient and high-quality products only when they are provided with high-quality raw materials. Of course, this makes it urgent for enterprises to increase efficiency in purchasing raw materials and actively search for suppliers of high-quality raw materials. Digitalization of the production process is today of great importance not only in improving product quality, but also in optimizing costs.

Today, effective mechanisms are being introduced to improve the quality of products manufactured by enterprises, increase their assortment, ensure competitiveness, find new markets, expand and support exports abroad. Many developed countries that have achieved success in exporting in the world have paid special attention to the quality of products, taking into account the needs and desires of customers, as well as to encouraging local manufacturers, as well as to fully localize production. Therefore, it is necessary to study the experiences of countries that have achieved great achievements and experience in this field and apply them in our economy. Major reforms are also being carried out in our country in terms of developing and constantly improving the products produced by enterprises based on foreign standards. Entering foreign markets with products produced by enterprises provides new opportunities for the enterprise, as well as ensuring financial stability and creating new jobs. It is important to increase the geography of exports when exporting manufactured products abroad.

In order to implement the identified important issues, reforms are being implemented in our republic to develop foreign economic activity. In the conditions of high demand for environmentally friendly products in the world, these reforms are bearing fruit. Entering foreign markets and finding new customers will serve as an important factor in the implementation of the strategic goals of enterprises in the future. Our government is carrying out systematic work in this

regard, and it is necessary to recognize various measures, various financial support tools and programs in order to comprehensively support and encourage enterprises that produce products and export them abroad. The main goal of this is to increase the number of enterprises, ensure their activities in various sectors, and ensure their versatility.

In addition, it is necessary to create a business and investment environment that is favorable in all respects for the effective operation of business entities in our country, as well as to improve the regulatory and legal framework, and to take effective measures in response to any adverse situations that arise. This is of great importance in supporting enterprises that pursue multiple goals. The effective operation and development of business entities is currently supported by the state, and this is one of the factors in their effective operation.

When optimizing the cost of production at enterprises, the following issues should be addressed:

- efficient and economical use of raw materials;
- attraction of energy-saving fixed assets to production;
- reduction of imports of raw materials due to the use of local raw materials.

In order to increase the country's export potential, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-85 dated June 3, 2024 "On further measures to accelerate market reforms and harmonize the national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the agreements of the World Trade Organization" and the Resolution No. PQ-179 dated May 15, 2024 "On measures to ensure the implementation of the agreements reached within the framework of the Third Tashkent International Investment Forum and the next meeting of the Foreign Investors Council" were adopted, as well as to ensure the implementation of export support measures in accordance with the agreements of the World Trade Organization. These documents are of great importance in increasing the export potential of our country.

References:

- 1.The Regulation "On the composition of costs for the production and sale of products (works, services) and the formation of financial results", approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 54 dated February 5, 1999. Tashkent. 1999.
- 2.Sobirov O. O. Improvement of management accounting in economic entities //Abstract of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation on Economic Sciences. Tashkent. TMI.-2022. – 2022.
- 3.Olimjonovich S. O. The Cost Of Forming A Management Account In Business Entities //Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. – 2022. – Т. 13.
- 4.Собиров О. О. Бошқарув ҳисобининг моҳияти ва уни ташкил этишда харажатларнинг ўрни //Scientific Journal of "International Finance& Accounting".-Т.: TMI.-2022. – 2022.
- 5.Otabek S., Uzokboyev R. Important Issues in the Organization of Work in Enterprises //Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521). – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 1018-1020.
- 6.Sobirov O. Improvement of financial reports to the level of international standards." //International Finance and Accounting" scientific journal. – 2021. – Т. 3.
- 7.Собиров О. Молиявий ҳ, исоботларни халцаро стандартлар талаблари даражасида такомиллаштириш.« //Халцаро молия ва ҳ, исоб» илмий журнали. – 2021. – Т. 3. – С. 2181-1016.

8. Sobirov O. O. Product Development Cost Factors Affecting Reduction // AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 07.

9. www.ziyo.net

10. www.lex.uz

